

INGLIZ TILINI CHET TILI SIFATIDA O'RGANAYOTGAN TALABALAR UCHUN "STEAM" TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN YANGI YONDASHUV SIFATIDA FOYDALANISH: "STEAM" KOMPETENSIYALAR TUSHUNCHASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda keng bahslarga sabab bo'layotgan "STEAM" ta'lim texnologiyasi asosida shakllantiriladigan "STEAM" kompetensiyalari va ularning til o'rganayotganlar uchun qay darajada muhimligi o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, "STEAM" texnologiyalarining dars jarayoniga targ'ib qilish usullari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: "STEAM" ta'limi, ijodkorlik, tanqidiy fikrlash, hamkorlik, innovatsiyalar, kognitiv "STEAM" kompetensiyalari va kognitiv bo'lmagan "STEAM" kompetensiyalari.

ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ "STEAM" ТЕХНОЛОГИИ КАК НОВЫЙ ПОДХОД ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ, ИЗУЧАЮЩИХ АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК КАК ИНОСТРАННЫЙ: ПОНЯТИЕ "STEAM" КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются компетенции "STEAM", которые формируются на основе широко обсуждаемой сегодня образовательной технологии "STEAM", и насколько они важны для изучающих язык. Также были обсуждены методы продвижения STEAM-технологий в учебный процесс.

Ключевые слова: Образование "STEAM", креативность, критическое мышление, сотрудничество, инновации, когнитивные компетенции "STEAM", и некогнитивные компетенции "STEAM".

INTEGRATING “STEAM” TECHNOLOGY AS A NEW APPROACH FOR THE STUDENTS LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE: THE CONCEPT OF “STEAM” COMPETENCES

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Annotation. This article examines “STEAM” competences built on the today’s much-discussed “STEAM” educational technology and how important they are for language learners. Methods for promoting “STEAM” technologies in the educational process are also discussed.

Keywords: “STEAM” education, creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, innovation, cognitive “STEAM” competences, and non-cognitive “STEAM” competences.

Introduction. The field of education, along with all other fields, needs reforming over the years. The 21st century is known as the age of technology in the history of the whole world. Incredible inventions, discoveries, and innovations have been created in several decades. At the moment, the process of globalization is accelerating all over the world. Today’s students are not only learning theoretically, but the main focus is practicing and implementing educational programs. No longer is only one subject taught, but the advantages of harmonizing and integrating education are becoming apparent to everyone day by day. One such approach is STEAM educational technology. The term STEM-science, which appeared in the USA in the early 1990s, is technology, engineering, mathematics, science, technology, engineering and mathematics integrated teaching as a goal. The main goal of doing this is to instill the novel skills of the 21st century in the young generation. National Science Foundation defines it this way: **STEAM** stands for Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics. It is an educational approach that integrates these disciplines to encourage interdisciplinary learning and problem-solving skills. The goal of STEAM education is to prepare students for the complex challenges of the 21st century by fostering these four skills:

- ⇒ **Creativity;**
- ⇒ **critical thinking;**
- ⇒ **collaboration;**
- ⇒ **innovation [1].**

Since this approach has appeared, STEAM competences have also come into the conversation. STEAM is a system of sciences supporting a new educational theory:

S – Science – natural sciences, the science of things and events that exist without participation of human factor. It covers Physics, Biology, Geography, Chemistry, Biochemistry, Cosmology, and Biotechnology;

T – Technology – technological sciences which is about creating tools to satisfy human needs and desires, including Energy, Transportation, Industry, Manufacturing, etc.;

E – Engineering – Engineering sciences are based on natural sciences, mathematics, logic and creative abilities with the help of technologies. Cosmic Engineering, Rural Construction Engineering, Mining Engineering, etc.;

M – Mathematics – operations on numbers. Algebra, Geometry, Data Science, Probability theory, Rural Construction Engineering, Mining Engineering, etc.;

A – Art – Arts sciences – it learns about the development of society, its effects, and traditions of today and the future.

1-picture: The logo of STEAM created by researcher G.Yakman

Literature review. International assessment programs for education and the issue of applying innovative technologies in education were studied by B.Kh.Khodjajev, M.Askarova, and G.Kasimova. Z.BSangirova, I.N.Kim, M.Kh.Toshbekova researched on the use of STEAM educational technology in the processes of integration training in pre-school and primary educational organizations [2, 259-265-p.].

Besides, scientific research on STEAM technologies is conducted by various individuals and institutions around the world. One notable example is Dr. Bronwyn Bevan, who has conducted research on the implementation and impact of STEAM education initiatives [3, 33-56-p.]. Dr. Kylie Pepler is another prominent researcher who has contributed significantly to studying of STEAM technologies. Her work often focuses on how digital media and technology can be integrated into arts and STEM education to enhance learning experiences [4, 158-165-p.]. Dr. Rebecca Callahan is

one researcher who has explored integrating of STEAM technologies into language learning. Her work investigates how incorporating elements of science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics elements can enhance language acquisition and proficiency, particularly among English language learners [5, 459-472-p.].

Research methodology. A survey of pertinent literature was conducted to look into integrating the STEAM approach in EFL training. Our investigation encompassed academic literature, peer-reviewed articles, and educational resources in order to learn about this approach's theoretical underpinnings and practical uses in language acquisition. We thoroughly reviewed pedagogical strategies and instructional methods for incorporating STEAM services, to identify best practices and practical implementation techniques. A comprehensive evaluation of the literature on educational technology, language acquisition theories, and teaching methodologies was conducted to explore the dynamic potential of integrating this novel approach into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction. Our investigation covered a wide range of sources, including academic publications, conference proceedings, and instructional websites, to gather insights into the most efficient methods and approaches for utilizing STEAM tools in language learning.

Analysis and results. The results section highlights several key findings from the collected materials. It emphasizes differentiated instruction as a crucial strategy that enables teachers to implement novelty in lessons and sometimes update assessment criteria to fit the individual learning needs of each student. It highlights integrating interdisciplinary approach to the learning and teaching process in order to encourage students' critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving skills among students. Integrating STEAM technology into language classrooms enhances language learning and cultivates interdisciplinary skills. Below are effective strategies for incorporating STEAM technology:

1. **Utilize Project-Based Learning (PBL):** Design language projects integrating STEAM, like crafting multimedia presentations on scientific topics or engineering solutions, coding language learning games, or creating artistic interpretations of mathematical concepts.

2. **Embrace Digital Storytelling:** Employ digital storytelling tools to blend language learning with technology. Students can craft multimedia narratives infused with science, technology, engineering, or math themes, honing language skills while expressing themselves creatively.

3. **Introduce Interactive Language Apps and Games:** Incorporate language learning apps and games with STEAM content, enabling interactive practice while engaging with STEM topics like math problems, virtual science experiments, or engineering challenges.

4. **Leverage Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR):** VR and AR technology can immerse students in language-rich environments related to STEM subjects. Students can explore virtual labs, historical sites, or digital simulations to practice language skills while learning STEM concepts.

5. **Integrate Coding and Computational Thinking:** Infuse coding activities and computational thinking exercises into language lessons. Students learn programming languages while practicing language skills or apply computational thinking to language-related tasks like analyzing patterns or developing translation algorithms.

6. **Assign STEM-themed Language Projects:** Task students with language projects focusing on STEM topics, such as researching scientific discoveries, writing technical reports on engineering advancements, or composing poetry inspired by math concepts. This will foster interdisciplinary learning and language proficiency.

7. **Facilitate Collaborative STEAM Projects:** Encourage collaborative projects uniting language learners with STEM students. Students exchange knowledge, perspectives, and language skills by collaborating on STEAM-themed projects, deepening their understanding of language and STEM concepts.

8. **Provide Professional Development and Resources:** Offer teachers training on integrating STEAM technology into language instruction. Workshops, online courses, and educational materials support the implementation of STEAM-infused language learning activities [6, 35-38-p.].

By integrating STEAM technology into language classrooms, educators can create immersive learning experiences that foster language proficiency, critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration across disciplines.

Researchers A.Carnevale, N.Smith, and M.Milton are the first who expressed their own views about STEAM competences and its components. These scientists divide STEAM competences into two parts: **cognitive STEAM competences** and **non-cognitive STEAM competences**.

STEAM competencies:

Cognitive STEAM competences: STEAM knowledge, STEAM skills, and STEAM abilities.

Non-cognitive STEAM competences: Curiosity towards STEM jobs and valuing STEM jobs.

Another study conducted in the USA like this by H.Jang. This scholar divides STEAM competences into five parts, which consist of knowledge, skill, and ability:

- ✓ Problem-solving (13 components)
- ✓ Teamwork (18 components)
- ✓ Working with technologies (6 components)
- ✓ Working with organizational structures (8 components)

- ✓ Working with resources (7 components) [7,290-p.].

Discussion. The discussion part highlights how important it is to incorporate STEAM-infused language learning into instruction to break down traditional silos between subjects and promote interdisciplinary learning. By integrating this method, students can gain a holistic understanding of how these disciplines are interconnected in the real world. Additionally, STEAM education encourages students to develop critical thinking skills by prompting them to evaluate complex issues, employ creative thinking, and devise innovative solutions. Through hands-on, inquiry-based learning experiences, students are empowered to draw upon knowledge from diverse disciplines to address authentic problems. In the modern era, many occupations require a combination of STEAM knowledge and creative skills. STEAM education equips students with the essential capabilities to excel in a dynamic job market, which includes adaptability, teamwork, and technological literacy. Since it encourages creativity and innovation, students are able to approach multiple perspectives, explore different solutions, and convey their ideas through creative methods [8]. Even though most scientists prefer only traditional methods, implementing STEAM education can assist learners in several ways and provide more benefits.

Conclusion/Recommendations. In conclusion, it can be said that the term “competence,” the combination of knowledge, skills, and, qualifications, is crucial to perform successfully in every field. Acquiring STEAM competences is required from learners to keeping up with the times and to excel 21st century skills. This field requires further research, commenting about it in several seminars, workshops and presentations. Incorporating STEAM principles into language learning shows great potential for enhancing educational experiences and promoting comprehensive skill growth. Moreover, STEAM in language education equips learners with the necessary abilities for success in today’s world, where effective communication, problem-solving, and technological proficiency are crucial. Through participation in hands-on projects, digital narrative creation, interactive applications, and collaborative STEAM endeavors, students can develop the aptitudes required to excel in an increasingly diverse and dynamic global community.

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